
CHARACTERIZATION OF MULBERRY (*Morus alba* L.) VARIETIES IN SOUTH WESTERN NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Stem cuttings of eight varieties of *Morus alba*, K2, NG1, S14, S41, S30, S34, S36 and S54 , obtained from the Sericulture Unit, Forestry Research Institute Of Nigeria (FRIN), Ibadan were planted with morphological characterization and chemical analysis done to determine the differences among them. Variety K2 showed a high performance in number of leaves produced with mean value of 4.09 and, have highest mean in plant height (5.09) and leaf area (9.46) respectively which is significantly different from the other varieties. However, S34 had the highest mean in stem girth with mean value of 1.516 which is significantly different from other varieties. NG1 has the highest mean in N and Fe, while the highest mean in C, Mg, K and P were observed in K2, S54, S30 and S54 respectively. K2 has high potentials that could be exploited for improvement of Mulberry germplasm for silkworm, livestock and human consumption while S34 apart from being useful as windbreaks and edges can also be exploited for its timber qualities and use in sport goods manufacture.

KEY WORDS: *Morus alba*, morphological characters, improvement, silkworm, stem cuttings, varieties

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INTRODUCTION

Morus is a complex genus, which belongs to the family Moraceae. According to plant scientists, it includes between 14-150 species (Huo, 2002; Martin *et al.*, 2002; Datta, 2002; Srivastava *et al.*, 2006). Although differing sources may cite *different* selections of accepted names, only 10–16 are generally cited as being accepted by the vast majority of botanical authorities. *Morus* classification is even further complicated by widespread hybridization, wherein the hybrids are fertile. Among species, *Morus alba* (white mulberry), *Morus nigra* (black mulberry) and *Morus rubra* (red mulberry) are wide spread throughout the world. *Morus alba* also called silkworm mulberry originated from Southwest China. (Yilmaz *et al.*, 2012).

Mulberry is cultivated under both tropical and temperate climatic conditions (Murthy *et al.*, 2010). They are swift growing and rarely exceed 10-15m (30-49ft) tall. The leaves are alternately arranged, simple or lobed, more often lobed on juvenile shoot than on mature tree and serrated on the margin. The fruit is a multiple fruit of about 2-3cm (0.79-1.2cm) long. White mulberry fruits are green when young and white when ripe, they are sweet but with a very mild flavour compared with darker variety.

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The main use of mulberry globally is as feed for the silkworm *Bombyx mori* L. but depending on the location, it is also appreciated for its fruit (consumed fresh, in juice or as preserves), as a delicious vegetable (young leaves and stems), for its medicinal properties in infusions (mulberry leaf tea), for landscaping as ornamental shade tree in shelterbelts and as animal feed (Stone, 2009). White mulberry species has been used exclusively in Chinese medicine since A.D- 659. The Chinese Pharmacopoeia lists the leaves, root bark, branches, and fruits as ingredients in medicinal preparations, but other parts, including the sap and wood ash, are also widely used to treat different ailments (Kumar and Chauhan, 2008; Zafar *et al.*, 2013). There are several places where mulberry is utilized traditionally as a feed in mixed diets for rabbit, poultry and cattle(Kasiviswanathan *et al.*, 1988; Al-Kirshi *et al.*, 2010; Bamikole *et al.*, 2005). *Morus alba* is highly shock resistance, not liable to split, and the wood is a blend of strength of elasticity and used for manufacturing rackets and toys. The wood 32% tannin is considered suitable for staining and colouring purposes. (NRCS/USDA,2003).

Minerals are chemical constituents and inorganic substances, present in all body tissues and fluids and used by the body in different ways. Their presence is necessary for the maintenance of certain physicochemical processes which are essential to life. Although they yield no energy, they have important roles to play in many activities in the body of organisms (Malhotra, 1998; Eruvbetine, 2003). Every form of living matter requires these inorganic elements or minerals for their normal life processes (Ozcan, 2003). Plants use these minerals as structural components in carbohydrates and proteins and as organic molecules in metabolism. Some of the essential elements that are required for the healthy growth of higher plants are examined in this study as listed by Epstein (1994).

Plants take in carbon in the form of atmospheric carbon dioxide, and take up the remaining elements from the soil. Mineral nutrients are essential chemical elements absorbed from the soil in the form of inorganic ions. Carbon is a major component of plant's organic compounds and its deficiency leads to growth retardation. Nitrogen is a component of nucleic acids, proteins, hormones, coenzymes and chlorophylls, its deficiency shows stunted growth, light green older leaves, older leaves become yellow and die (chlorosis). Magnesium is a component of chlorophylls, and activates many enzymes, its deficiency causes chlorosis and drooped leaves. Iron is a component of cytochromes, functions in electron transport, activation of some enzymes, and plays a role in chlorophyll synthesis. Its deficiency leads to chlorosis in plants. Potassium is a cofactor that functions in protein synthesis, activation of enzymes, water balance and thus affecting osmosis and stomata operation. Its deficiency results in reduced growth, curled, mottled, or spotted older leaves, burned leaf margins, weakened roots and stems. Phosphorus is a component of nucleic acids, phospholipids, adenosine triphosphate (ATP), several coenzymes and its deficiency results in purplish veins in older leaves, fewer seeds and fruits and stunted growth. (Uchida,2000).

It is important to regularly obtain up-to-date information on the mineral content of plants used for human and animal foods and feeds respectively because of the effects of chemicals like pesticides, herbicides, fertilizers on the mineral contents of the soils where these plants are cultivated. Genetic, location and environmental factors could also influence the levels of the mineral elements in plants. (Soetan *et al.*, 2010).

The many uses of mulberry offer a challenging task to the germplasm resources across the globe, in exploration and collection of fruits yielding mulberry species; their characterization, cataloguing and evaluation of such ingredients by using traditional as well as modern means and bio technology tools; developing an information system about these mulberry species; training and global coordination of utilization of these genetic stocks and finally in evolving suitable breeding strategies to improve the several active biomolecules in the potential breeds by collaboration with various research stations in the field of sericulture, plant genetics , breeding, biotechnology and pharmacology.

The objective of this study therefore is to characterize eight *Morus alba* varieties using morphological and chemical parameters with a view to recommending the best variety for sericultural and other uses.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental site

The experiment was carried out at Forestry Technology Department nursery (Nursery B) of the Federal College of Forestry Jericho, Ibadan Nigeria (Long 3^o54' E and Lat 7^o23'N) with a mean total rainfall (1420.06mm), temperature (23.44^o C) and relative humidity of 65%. The experiment was carried out from October to December, 2012.

Materials used

The materials for this project are two- nodal stem cuttings of eight varieties of *Morus alba*: “NG1, K2, S14, S30, S34, S36, S41 and S54”; obtained from the Sericulture Unit, Forestry Research Institute Of Nigeria (FRIN), Ibadan Nigeria.

Topsoil was collected from the College Arboretum, Federal College of Forestry, Ibadan.

Preparation of experimental soil

The experimental soil was sieved before potting to remove clogs of soil, stones and weeds and potted into well perforated polythene pots. Data collection started two weeks after planting. Watering was done twice daily and weeding when necessary.

Data collection

Morphological parameters (number of leaves, plant height, stem girth and leaf area) were assessed and recorded on weekly basis. Also, five chemical elements (Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Iron, Carbon and Magnesium) were analyzed.

Data analysis

The data obtained were analyzed using CRD (Completely Randomized Design) according to the methods of Steel and Tore (1980) while Duncan Multiple Range Test was used to test the level of significant of the means (Duncan, 1955).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: The result of morphological characterization of eight varieties of *Morus alba*

Varieties	Mean Leaf Number	Mean height (cm)	Mean girth (cm)	Mean Leaf Area (cm)
NG1	3.10 ^{bcd}	3.24 ^{bcd}	1.332 ^{bc}	6.73 ^{ab}
K2	4.09 ^a	5.09 ^a	1.083 ^d	9.46 ^a
S14	3.19 ^{bc}	3.21 ^{bcd}	1.364 ^b	5.96 ^{bc}
S30	3.69 ^{ab}	3.94 ^b	1.189 ^{cd}	7.31 ^{ab}
S34	3.16 ^{bc}	3.43 ^{bc}	1.311 ^{bc}	6.15 ^{bc}
S36	2.27 ^d	2.08 ^d	1.362 ^b	3.25 ^c
S41	3.02 ^{bcd}	2.97 ^{bcd}	1.325 ^{bc}	5.82 ^{bc}
S54	2.75 ^{cd}	2.66 ^{cd}	1.516 ^a	4.55 ^{bc}

Note: ^{a,b,c..} Any two means having a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance.

Considering the number of leaves, K2 showed high performance, with mean value of 4.09 which is significantly different from the other varieties, this could provide large volume of food for rearing silkworm. However in the area of protein content examined by Venkalesh and Seema (2011), S36, which produced the least amount of leaves

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provide more protein for the worms. Further breeding work can however combine these properties in the two varieties to produce a desirable hybrid. Also, variety S30 is next with mean leaf number of 3.69. Varieties S14, S30, NG1, S41, S54, show similarities and are not significantly different while S36 had the least performance with mean leave number of 2.27. The treatment K2 compared with NG1, S14, S30, S34, S36, S41, S54, shows a large difference on the mean leaf number between the varieties.

Variety K2 performed best in plant height with mean value of 5.09m and it is significantly different. This is an advantage in its use as vegetable for man and animals according to the works of Datta, (1992) and supported by Adeduntan and Oyerinde (2010) that it is rich in essential minerals which is readily available. This is followed by S30 with a mean height of 3.94m. The varieties NG1, S14, S34, K2 and S54 show similarities and are not significantly different while S34 had the least performance with mean height of value 2.08m. Varieties K2 (5.09) and S30 (3.94) compared with S14, S34, S36, S41 and S54 show a large difference in the mean height values.

The result on girth shows that S54 performed best with mean value of 1.516 and it is significantly different from all other varieties. This, apart from being useful as windbreaks and edges can also be exploited for its timber qualities and use in sport ware manufacture (NRCS/USDA, 2003). S14 performed next with 1.364 mean girth. The varieties NG1, S41, S34, and S30 show similarities but are not significantly different while K2 had the least performance with mean girth of 1.083. Varieties S54 (1.516) and S14 (1.364) compared with NG1, K2, S30, S34, S41; and S54 compared with S14 shows a large difference on the mean girth value between the varieties.

The result on the leaf area shows that K2 performed best with mean value of 9.46 and it is significantly different from all other varieties. S30 performed next with mean leaf area 7.31. The varieties K2 (9.46) & S30 (7.31) compared with NG1, S14, S36, S41, and S54 show a large difference in the leaf area among the varieties. K2 having the highest mean in leaf area goes further to support foliage availability for silkworm, livestock and human consumption (Venkalesh and Seema, 2011). The Variety NG1 with mean (6.73), S34 (6.15), S41 (5.82) and S54 (4.55) show similarities and are not significantly different while, S36 had the least performance on leaf area with mean value of 3.25.

Table 2: The result of chemical analysis of eight varieties of *Morus alba*

Varieties	N %	C(mg/100g)	Mg ⁺⁺ (mg/100g)	Fe ⁺⁺ (mg/100g)	K+ (mg/100g)	P(mg/100g)
NG1	2.09 ^a	54.52 ^{bc}	14.35 ^c	9.40 ^a	24.35 ^c	145 ^a
K2	1.97 ^c	54.70 ^a	13.90 ^d	8.65 ^c	25.25 ^b	140 ^a
S14	1.92 ^d	53.85 ^{cd}	14.30 ^c	8.80 ^c	24.45 ^c	150 ^a
S30	1.98 ^c	53.30 ^e	15.05 ^{ab}	9.30 ^a	26.30 ^a	145 ^a
S34	2.04 ^b	54.25 ^{bc}	13.45 ^e	9.30 ^a	24.00 ^c	145 ^a
S36	1.87 ^e	53.65 ^{de}	15.10 ^{ab}	9.15 ^{ab}	25.35 ^b	140 ^a
S41	2.04 ^b	54.55 ^{ab}	14.85 ^b	9.30 ^a	25.40 ^b	145 ^a
S54	1.92 ^d	54.15 ^{bc}	15.25 ^a	8.90 ^{bc}	25.70 ^b	150 ^a

Note: ^{a,b,c...} Any two means having a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance.

From Table 2, the Nitrogen % of the S14 and S54; K2 and S30; and S34 and S41 are not significantly different from each other while S36 and NG1 are significantly different from each other and from the remaining varieties. To select or recommend the best variety treatment, NG1 could be recommended because it has the highest Nitrogen % level followed by S34 and S41. Nitrogen is an essential component of all proteins, and proteins are essential to quality cocoon production in sericulture.

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The Total organic carbon of the varieties S30 and S36; S14 and S36; S14,S54, NG1 and S34 ; S54,NG1,S34,and S41; S41 and K2 are not significantly different from each other (Table 2) . K 2 and S41 have been observed in this study to have the highest total organic carbon level, followed by NG1, S34 and S54.

From Table 2 also, the Magnesium ion concentration of the varieties S14 and NG1; S41, S30 and S36; S30, S36 and S54; are not significantly different from each other while S34 and K2 are significantly different from each other and the other varieties. The study revealed that variety S54 had the highest Magnesium ion level followed by S36 and S30. Adeduntan and Oyerinde (2010) however observed that S 36 have the highest magnesium content while K 2 and S 54 had the same value.

From Table 2, the Iron ion concentration of the varieties K2, S14 and S54; S54 and S36; S36, S30,S34 ,S41 and NG1 are not significantly different from one another. NG1 has the highest mean Iron ion concentration of 9.40, while varieties S30, S34, S36, and S41 could also be considered. This same trend was observed in Iron concentration by Adeduntan and Oyerinde (2010) in their study involving varieties K2, S54 and S36.

Table 2 also revealed that potassium ion concentration of varieties S34, NG1 and S14; K2, S36, S41 and S54 are not significantly different from one another, while S30 is significantly different from the other varieties and has the highest mean of 26.30. Adeduntan and Oyerinde, (2010), in their experiment however observed S36 to be higher in Potassium when compared with other varieties.

The level of Phosphorus was found to be the same in varieties K2 and S36 (140mg/100g); varieties NG1, S30, S34 and S41 (145mg/100g) and varieties S14 and S54 (150mg/100g). The test statistic shows that the data available are the same which indicates no significant difference in their means. It is therefore concluded that the test on Phosphorus is indefinite. Phosphorus is an essential macronutrient for plants and one of the three nutrients generally added to soils in fertilizers because of its vital role of energy transfer in living organisms and in plants. Adequate phosphorus availability stimulates early growth and hastens maturity in plants (Sharma *et al.*, 2008).

CONCLUSION

Considering the number of leaves, plant height, and leaf area, variety K2 showed a high performance which is significantly different from other varieties, while S34 had the highest mean in stem girth which is also significantly different from the other varieties, and these can be exploited as discussed above. Going by the analysis of chemical elements, NG1 has the highest mean in N and Fe, while the highest mean in C, Mg, K and P were observed in K2, S54, S30 and S54 respectively. Great variability had been observed in the *Morus alba* varieties studied. This has opened another avenue to research into other uses to which this species can be put and ways to improve them for use in our environment. This could provide alternatives to a lot of plant resources being overexploited and driven to the verge of extinction.

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